

#D1.3

Final documentation of events

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i. Document history

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1. Introduction

We - as a consortium - started this journey three years ago, with the ambition to create and build a worldwide community and platform for open personalised healthcare solutions. With a strong belief in the necessity of such a platform and the need within society. These last years we embarked on a 'roadtrip' to engage with communities, introduced Careables and organised workshops to inform and educate healthcare professionals, makers, designers and above all people with healthcare challenges. We encountered great people, spread our message and over the years our platform grew in numbers of members and numbers of careables. These encounters, workshops and presentations have shown that the need within society is strong, and it takes time to create impact and change within the healthcare system.

The aim of this report is to provide an overview and report all activities that took place. This ranges from presentations at conferences to small workshops and from training students and healthcare professionals to present at maker faires. A large number of events were hosted by the partners. The partners also attended and contributed to events organised by affiliated partners or were invited by organisations to present. This report is an overview of the events that we have organised or contributed to. In three years around 300 events took place. All activities are categorised by type of activity and reported by category.

The last year of the project changed due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Numerous events that were planned needed to be scaled down or remodelled for a digital audience. However, the maker community stepped up in the crisis, putting the experiences in personalised healthcare solutions into practice. In the overview, we provide a detailed overview of COVID-19 related activities.

i. Objectives

This report is the final deliverable of WP 1 Engagement and community growth. The main objective of this deliverable is to report on the activities that were conducted by the partners and the network of affiliated partners. It describes the overview of all activities, but above all provides insights on the community engagement and growth that

was achieved within the project.

Within the community engagement, we identified several types of activities. The engagement activities aimed to identify the needs of the communities, but also sensitise the active involvement of citizens in the co-design and delivery of open healthcare solutions. Each type of activity contributes to specific aspects of community engagement. To make it comprehensible, the report describes the overview per type of activity in a visual presentation. Also, the training experiences that took place within the project are reported in this document.

ii. Project strategy

In the proposal, we envisioned a strategy to engage and grow the community. This was focussed on both local and global engagement activities. Starting from the partner Fab Labs, connect to local communities of citizens with (physical) healthcare needs, carers, and healthcare professionals with the community of makers, and grow the engagement to a national, European and global level by collaborating with affiliated Fab Labs, communities and healthcare organisations.

Figure 1 : Engagement strategy

The project strategy was to engage stakeholder communities, bring these existing communities together and connect them in the field of open source healthcare solutions. The engagement focussed on both local levels as well as global engagement.

The first year focussed on **local outreach and events** within the partner Fab Labs and their communities and cities. With a focus on the local context, we were able to experiment with different types of events, channels and content to reach out to the local communities. We

were also able to identify the needs of our different target groups. The first year allowed us to develop the Careables-platform.

In the second year of Careables we continued the **local outreach** and started the **global outreach** to affiliated partners, to GIG members and to communities worldwide. We used the insights of the local activities to transfer these to other locations and affiliated partners. We also organised training and education activities at healthcare organisations, schools, and universities. By developing a toolkit we were able to share our knowledge and provide practical information on how to start working on open source healthcare solutions. Furthermore, the Careables-platform was available for outside contributions.

In the last year, the engagement focussed on the **sustainability** of activities within the global community. We continued to improve the platform, adding features, and growing the number of documented careables. The consortium partners continued the dissemination and exploitation of the results and organised the moving exhibition. And formulated a plan to maintain the Careables-platform and activities after the project period.

In the engagement strategy (D1.1) we introduced a circle model to plot the different stakeholder groups. This model can be used to clarify the different types of engagement.

Figure 2: Circular engagement model

The model consists of three circles. Each place in this circle is now further elaborated on:

- Outside the circle // People who are not aware of the platform or project and will not automatically understand the value of combining open source maker practices with health care-related challenges. This group should be presented with a clear explanation of why this unique cross-over and multidisciplinary approach is worth learning more about. We aim for this group to get aware of the concepts and ideas that are the base for Careables-project.
- Aware // People in this layer of the circle are aware of communities like the 'Maker Movement' and/or the need for tailor-made health care solutions. They might have seen open source hardware projects benefiting society before and can imagine the power of the cross-over between these worlds.
- Informed // People who are informed and had an interaction with Careables-project in some form. They've seen a presentation, online content, or had contact with people involved in the project. These people, who are aware of the project plan, and informed on some of the activities will be triggered to participate.
- Participant // Participation in Careables could have many forms. This can be joining an event, collaborating on the platform, or sharing challenges with the community. The main goal of participation relates to the platform Careables. Participation leads to challenging identification, prototyping and development.

iii. Event types

The events were categorised in type of activities. The following activities were identified:

- open days
- experience workshops
- training and education
- maker gatherings
- presentations
- exhibitions

The **Open days** aimed to involve citizens, healthcare professionals, designers, and makers to learn and ideate on personalised healthcare solutions. Open days were public events, open to everybody interested. The format of the open days was flexible, ranging from a presentation and dialogue to more hands-on sessions, where participants could tinker. It could be organised around a specific topic or careable. The main aims of an open day were to inspire and create awareness among stakeholders and the general public, to explore the possibilities of Careables, and to start the development, prototype of solutions. Due to the open accessibility for a broad audience, we also classify Meetups as an Open day.

The **Experience workshops** were hands-on workshops, where participants learned how to co-design and co-produce open healthcare solutions. The workshops enabled participants to start the co-design process, prototyping and to experience collaboration with people with healthcare challenges, healthcare professionals, designers, and makers.

Training and education focussed on educating students and healthcare professionals on the principles of Careables and teaching them the skills needed to co-design and co-develop careables. A toolkit was developed to support these training activities. The training sessions took place at the partner Fab Labs, at healthcare organisations, and universities. The activities varied in time from one training session to multiple sessions.

Fab Labs and makerspaces have numerous platforms and networks at their disposal to collaborate. The **Maker gatherings** aimed to inform labs and makerspaces on open healthcare solutions and supported the knowledge exchange between the labs. These events were specifically targeted towards the community of makers and designers. The maker community engages with a broader audience by organising maker faires. Also, workshops and presentations that were organised at the European maker faires are included as maker gatherings.

Presentations are held to inform the audience on open healthcare solutions, the Careables platform, and the process of co-design and co-development. The audience consisted of citizens (people with healthcare questions, carers), healthcare professionals, makers, designers, researchers, policy makers, commercial companies, and

the general public at large.

And the last category that is identified, is **Exhibitions**. Careables was showcased at several large annual fairs, like Dutch Design Week, Milano Salone de Mobile (Design Collisions). But also in smaller venues, Careables was exhibited. The exhibitions varied in time from one day to a month.

Although we have this clear distinction between these types of activities, the classification of them is not always that obvious. Organising an event often meant that a mix of these activities was executed. I.e. an evening for healthcare professionals, people with healthcare challenges, and carers start with a general presentation on Careables and continues with an experience workshop.

Furthermore, several events were programmed over multiple days. These multi-day events often contained several types of activities. I.e. at the maker fair partners gave both a presentation and a workshop. In this report, the events are classified into one category as much as possible. Some events with multiple activities are classified into several categories.

Open Days	Participants
59	1,316
Workshops	Participants
34	1,937
Education	Participants
54	3,072
Maker Gatherings	Participants
31	19,279
Presentations	Participants
114	24,780
Exhibitions	Participants
14	84,880
All	Participants
306	135,264

2. Events in numbers

Throughout the three years of the Careables-project the partners and affiliated partners executed 306 events and organised or participated in 14 exhibitions.

Events by type (2018-2020)

As the last year focussed on engaging affiliated makerspaces and Fab Labs, and aimed to expand our community, this all changed due to the COVID-19-pandemic. The anticipated Open Days (organised by these makerspaces) could only partly be organised. A large part of the events was organised online. This allowed participants to join relatively easily, but it was difficult to engage new audiences. The collaboration with existing communities of healthcare professionals intensified in COVID-19-related activities and the development of COVID-19-careables. However, reaching out to new groups of healthcare professionals was very difficult. A more detailed description of the COVID-19-related activities is given in chapter 3.

Overview of Careables Events by Year

In the graphs below the events are plotted throughout the three-year project period.

Overview of Careables Countries by Continent

The Careables-project started in 2018 in the partner countries and grew over the project period to a community with global reach and activities. The partners were invited by affiliated partners, commercial and healthcare organisations to present the notion of open healthcare solutions and Careables. Also, the GIG-members started to organise local activities and collaborated with local communities. The outreach of the events was in 22 countries worldwide (as shown in the graph below).

We engaged with the international community of Fab Labs. Open Dot and Waag hosted workshops and presentations at the International Fab Conference in 2018 and 2019 where 1600 makers gathered. The 2020 edition was fully online, under the name FabXLive. Careables was presented online by Open Dot.

Map of Carables Maker Faires & Presentations

Careables was presented at numerous Maker Faires every year. Open Dot, Prototypes (formerly Fab Lab Berlin), KUL, and ZSI attended Maker Faires in Torino, Rome, Zagreb, Berlin, and Vienna. Furthermore, we had the opportunity to present Careables at Re:publica (Berlin), the Embassy of Health during the Dutch Design Week (Eindhoven), and Salone di Mobile (Milano) yearly. In addition, we were invited for a presentation at Europe's largest medical fair Medica (Düsseldorf).

Key

- Exhibitions
- Maker Faires

For the moving exhibition, we developed a guide and visual identity that partners and affiliated partners were able to use. The main aim of the moving exhibition was to showcase locally designed and developed Careables, but also highlight that Careables is a global community. The global community was shown by a print of a world map, with local initiatives (location, short description, and picture) positioned in the map. Based on the local possibilities some videos of initiatives could be added. This setup enables partners to have an identical look & feel, but be flexible to adjust to the local setting of the exhibition space that was available. Furthermore, this setup prevented a lot of shipping of materials. Due to the COVID-19-restrictions, several possibilities to exhibit were cancelled.

In total 93 dedicated Open Days were hosted, reaching 3.253 participants. This is a combination of Open Days and Experience workshops. From March 2020 the planned Open Days and workshops were cancelled due to COVID-19. Only part of the events was transformed into an online format. The active contribution of organising Open Days by affiliated labs, as foreseen in the proposal during the last year, were altered. Regular Open Days to invite and engage with new local communities was feasible. However many of the affiliated labs within the Fab Lab network were very active in COVID-19-related careables. They opened their facilities and started designing and producing as well as replicating COVID-19-careables.

The project partners presented Careables in 114 presentations. This is an increase of almost 50% than initially planned in the proposal. The presentations were given at healthcare-related events, national and international conferences, and locally organised events. A large number of presentations that were given in 2020 were online. This increased the audience. 24.780 people attended the presentations in total.

The number of members in the Meetup groups grew to 6.058 members in total.

- **Make Health group Amsterdam (Waag): 914 members**
- **Fab Lab Berlin Meet Up Group: 4.578 members**
- **Facebook-group & Mailinglist Opendot: 566 members.**

This is three times the anticipated number of members (in the proposal 2.000 members were noted).

Careables was present at 31 Maker gatherings, including the international Fab Conference, Maker Faires. The partners gave presentations, hosted workshops, and showcased Careables. In total 19.279 people were reached.

In total 54 training and educational events were organised by the project partners and 3.072 people were trained. The total number of participants was less than the anticipated 4.500 participants. The main reason is that the training of healthcare professionals was cut short of COVID-19. And also took additional efforts to set up training

activities in online formats. The partners developed a toolkit, based on their learnings, for Fab Labs and makerspaces. This toolkit shares both knowledge and practical guidelines that enable other interested makerspaces to start with open health solutions. And is free of charge available on the website.

The public debates were aimed to engage a larger audience of policy makers, government officials, and managers. In the debates, we would reflect on the insights gathered, provide information about the context and engage in a discussion on possibilities for broad implementation. Publication of Careables research and insights in papers also contributed to feeding into the public debates. I.e. the paper on legal challenges of open source hardware and collaborative platforms - Biasin, E and Kamenjašević, E. 2020. Open Source Hardware and Healthcare Collaborative Platforms: Common Legal Challenges. Journal of Open Hardware, 4(1): 7, pp. 1–8. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5334/joh.31>

2.1 Some experiences

There have been almost 300 events organised, hosted and attended in this project. For each event, a story or an anecdote can be told. To keep this report as visual as possible, we've included several more personal experiences based on some events from the partners.

“Careables project was my first connection with disabilities and disability has entered my daily life at TOG in the shape of smiling children waving their hands while they walk to the therapist door. I am interested in languages and I have always observed the hyper-political correctness in talking of disabilities and in some ways I tried to comply with it. When I participated in co-design sessions at the Health&care summer school or Careables meet up, I realized that all these cautions are simply unnecessary. The practice of listening openly, letting stereotypes aside, generates true dialogue and mutual understanding. It is empathy and it is human” - TOG

“Presenting Careables at international conferences has been a challenge and a reward! It's quite challenging to pack all the great careables experiences into short presentations, but the reaction of the audience has always been fantastic. The best experiences were made when telling personal stories of careables users, who benefited from the co-design and replication of personalised solutions.” - ZSI

“Organising the Make Health prototyping series was intense, but also very inspiring and rewarding. Over 40 participants started the first week, and it was a challenge to form the teams. But during the workshop series, they really got into the process and were eager to design and create tangible solutions. The participants experienced that personalised solutions could be made. It opened up their way of thinking, and for us as well. We realised that the process made a difference.” - WAAG

“Nepal Communitere along with Field Ready was curious how we would be able to engage engineers and makers to work with different communities to address their health needs. Whether it was health providers working with children who have cerebral palsy or young engineering, design, and business students to use human-centered approaches to co-create solutions - we all walked away with learnings. The key learning and brilliant aha moment were how

necessary it is to prototype and get direct feedback from users themselves and then engage them in the iteration process. It was also great to see makers and engineers not have to design products from scratch but pull from open-source platforms to adapt and iterate and then share their adapted products back to the larger community. It helped them feel like they truly are part of a larger maker community!" - Communitere Nepal (GIG)

"Careables is so much! How to pack it into 20-minute presentations? Raising awareness has best worked with personal stories from careables users. People who benefit directly from co-design and replications of personalized healthcare solutions and those who help them realize it are the ones who should get the attention." - ZSI

"Careables helped increase our community's knowledge about open-source, digital manufacturing and health care to the involved stakeholders: physicists, designers, healthcare professionals, and makers and allowed Casa Criatura to review its activities with a more significant focus on what is to care." - Casa Criatura Brasil, GIG

"With Careables.org I've witnessed how important it is for people with disabilities to be able to see that aids can be adapted to each person's necessity and that they don't have to be impossible to get because of their price and set features. Said so, it was very inspiring and uplifting to see that what Careables.org offered was useful, interesting, and exciting for them. A world full of possibilities." - Opendot

"Exhibiting three careables during the Dutch Design Week was an endeavour. With the help of the initiators, like Debby and Alle, we engaged with so many visitors to the exhibition for nine days. Careables resonated with them as many of them had similar experiences with medical tools, and it was great to see the spark of Careables-potential ignite during these encounters." - WAAG

"Careables has been a constituting project for GIG that has helped excel our community. Careables brings together a number of topics and approaches that are central to our network, our values, and our aims under the roof of one project - openness, caring, collaboration, and respect for the individual. Many members of our network had pre-existing relevant activities and others used the opportunity to create new projects in their hubs and makerspaces. Careables acted

as an accelerator, connecting members working on similar issues, seeking to find new solutions, and service their communities. This was especially true during COVID-19. We look forward to continuing the Careables project, building more Careables around the world and expanding the network." - GIG

"Getting across the message that aids work better/are better if tailor-made to specific needs was what we aimed to do when we designed the Glifo Kickstarter campaign. Being able to provide this kind of service to children who want and need to channel their creativity without compromising their rehabilitation process is fundamental. Being part of such a project and achievement was a wonderful boost and incredible experience!" - Opendot

3.Careables & COVID-19

The COVID-19-pandemic not only changed the anticipated events during the last year. It also brought new collaborations and a stage for Careables. Our health systems faced unexperienced pressure, with failing supply chains and shortage of personal safety materials. The maker communities immediately started to prototype, local produce and globally share designs of COVID-19-related careables, such as face shields, door openers, and other medical supplies. They managed to supply the healthcare system with the needed materials and equipment.

The central process of Careables - the collaboration of healthcare professionals, people with healthcare questions, makers, and designers - was adopted by makerspaces around the world. Not only the sharing of designs, replication, and adjustments of personal protection equipment, numerous grassroots initiatives were alongside industrial and commercial partners to provide the needed medical supplies. It showcased the potential of how makerspaces can contribute to our healthcare system and supply chain.

A paper, describing several Careables initiatives on COVID-19-response was published: COVID-19 response from global makers: the Careables cases of global design and local production (2020). B. Kieslinger, T. Schäfer, C.M. Fabian, E. Biasin, E. Bassi, R. Ruiz Freire, N. Mohow, N. Arif & P. Melis.

Multiple public debates, i.e. at re:publica TV, Pakhuis de Zwijger and several conferences, all discussed the process of open health solutions and the impact that makerspaces made within the healthcare domain. These were all online debates or talks (as webinar of live broadcast).

12	Presentations
3	Workshops (incl. 1 training)
3	Maker gatherings (incl. 1 training & presentation)
1	Exhibition
3	Hackathons
22	Events in total

Table 1: Overview of COVID19-related events

4. Conclusions & lessons learned

In the three years, the project has been full of events and activities. Based on the engagement strategy the partners experimented with different types of activities. Activities that would fit the needs of local communities best. Although we've categorised the events in types, each activity was unique. Each time the formats were adapted and tailored to the needs of the context and participants. Also, each country is different, as is the healthcare services in each country. This has taught us that there is no uniform way of engaging with our communities.

Over the years we also learned that it takes time and effort to include people with unmet needs or physical limitations. Including healthcare professionals also takes time and training. They need to experience how design processes and digital fabrication techniques can be of added value to healthcare, as well as they experience new tasks as a professional.

This process of engagement has shown us that Careables can really impact a person's life. And that the process of co-design and co-production is viable. Although the last year changed dramatically, Careables was a solid way of working as COVID19-response. Many makerspaces stepped up and started collaborating to provide personal protective equipment and medical supplies.

As partners we managed to learn from each other, exchanging insights on how to engage communities and execute our events. With local differences and within the Careables-identity. We feel that the last three years have provided us with a great opportunity to build the network. Several partners will continue their work within Careables and expand the network, include new makerspaces, welcome more ambassadors, and let the platform grow further to be an inspiration for everybody.

Activity Report

i. Workshops

Workshop

21-25 August 2019
Chaos Communication Camp
Participants: 8
Organiser: Chaos Computer Club
Location: Zehdenick, Germany

Workshop

4 December 2019
Careables Luncheon
Participants: 14
Organiser: Global Innovation Gathering
Location: Nairobi, Kenya

December

October

5-6 December 2019
Careables Track at DOTS – The Impact Summi

Participants: 8
Organiser: Global Innovation Gathering, r0g agency, Cadus e.V.
Location: Nakuru, Kenya

Workshop

30 October 2019
Health&care Industry day

Participants: 22
Organiser: Opendot
Location: Milano, Italy

Workshop

7 December 2019
DOTS – The Impact Summit (public day)

Participants: 70
Organiser: Global Innovation Gathering, r0g agency, Cadus e.V.
Location: Nakuru, Kenya

Workshop

Activity Report

ii. Trainings/Education

2020

January

**January – March 2020
Careables AT Kumasi Training**

Participants: 18
Organiser: Kumasi Hive
Location: Kumasi, Ghana
M4Y Representation: GIG

Training

March

Training

**1 – 17 March 2020
Open Health Hackademy#1**

Participants: 37
Organiser: Prototypes, be able, MachBar, HPI
Location: Berlin, Germany
M4Y Representation: Prototypes

February

**3 February 2020
Presentation students (2nd year)
Royal Academy of the Arts**

Participants: 24
Organiser: Royal Academy of the Arts
Location: Amsterdam, the Netherlands
M4Y Representation: Waag

Training

**2 March 2020
Recitation about digital fabrication in
healthcare during the fab academy**

Participants: 60
Organiser: Fabacademy
Location: online
M4Y Representation: Opendot & Waag

Training

May

Training

23 May 2020
Design and 3D technologies for Health&Care – Summer School courses/ Custom orthotics

Participants: 27
 Organiser: DDMP project together with careables
 Location: online
 M4Y Representation: Opendot

Training

16 June 2020
Design and 3D technologies for Health&Care Summer School courses/Parametric Design

Participants: 30
 Organiser: DDMP project together with careables
 Location: online
 M4Y Representation: Opendot

Training

26 June 2020
Design and 3D technologies for Health&Care Summer School courses/ Training kit for the medical staff

Participants: 24
 Organiser: DDMP project together with careables
 Location: online
 M4Y Representation: Opendot

June

6 June – 9 August 2020
Open Health HACKademy#3

Participants: 60
 Organiser: Prototypes, be able e.V.
 Location: Berlin, Germany
 M4Y Representation: Prototypes

17 June 2020
Open Health HACKademy#3 Public Feedbackmeeting 1

Participants: 34
 Organiser: Prototypes, be able e.V.
 Location: online
 M4Y Representation: Prototypes

19 June 2020
Design and 3D technologies for Health&Care Summer School courses/Modeling for surgery

Participants: 21
 Organiser: DDMP project together with careables
 Location: online
 M4Y Representation: Opendot

Training

Training

Training

Activity Report

iii. Open Days

June

1 June 2018
Careables Meetup Fablab Berlin 3
 Participants: 20
 Organiser: Fablab Berlin (now Prototypes)
 Location: Berlin, Germany

Open Day

7 June 2018
Made 4 You series (Open Call) 1.4
 Participants: 25
 Organiser: Waag
 Location: Amsterdam, The Netherlands

Open Day

21 June 2018
Made 4 You series (Open Call) 1.6
 Participants: 25
 Organiser: Waag
 Location: Amsterdam, The Netherlands

Open Day

29 June 2018
Careables Meetup Fablab Berlin 5
 Participants: 16
 Organiser: Fablab Berlin (now Prototypes)
 Location: Berlin, Germany

Open Day

7 June 2018
3rd Meetup Opendot (hackabilityMilano)
 Participants: 20
 Organiser: Milano Luiss Hub for makers and students
 Location: Milano, Italy

Open Day

28 June 2018
Made 4 You series (Open Call) 1.7
 Participants: 25
 Organiser: Waag
 Location: Amsterdam, The Netherlands

Open Day

14 June 2018
Made 4 You series (Open Call) 1.5
 Participants: 25
 Organiser: Waag
 Location: Amsterdam, The Netherlands

Open Day

Open Day

23 September 2018
Prototyping Fridays

Participants: 12
Organiser: Fablab Berlin (now Prototypes)
Location: Berlin, Germany

30 September 2018
Careables Meetup Fablab Berlin 7

Participants: 20
Organiser: Fablab Berlin (now Prototypes)
Location: Berlin, Germany

Open Day

Open Day

15 October 2018
Debby White cane event

Participants: 15
Organiser: Waag
Location: Amsterdam, The Netherlands

29 September 2018
Made 4 You series (Open Call) 2.2

Participants: 50
Organiser: Waag
Location: Amsterdam, The Netherlands

Open Day

October

6 October 2018
Made 4 You series (Open Call) 2.3

Participants: 45
Organiser: Waag
Location: Amsterdam, The Netherlands

Open Day

20 October 2018
Made 4 You series (Open Call) 2.4

Participants: 45
Organiser: Amsterdam, The Netherlands
Location: Waag

Open Day

November

Open Day

3 November 2018
Made 4 You series (Open Call) 2.5
Participants: 40
Organiser: Waag
Location: Amsterdam, The Netherlands

Open Day

8 November 2018
Extra open night Made4You Teams
Participants: 25
Organiser: Waag
Location: Amsterdam, The Netherlands

Open Day

29 November 2018
Careables meet up November
Participants: 10
Organiser: Opendot
Location: Milano, Italy

Open Day

10 November 2018
Made 4 You series (Open Call) 2.6
Participants: 40
Organiser: Waag
Location: Amsterdam, The Netherlands

Open Day

7 November 2018
Extra open night Made4You Teams
Participants: 30
Organiser: Waag
Location: Amsterdam, The Netherlands

Open Day

20 November 2018
Extra open night Made4You Teams
Participants: 20
Organiser: Waag
Location: Amsterdam, The Netherlands

December

Open Day

4 December 2018
Extra open night Made4You Teams
Participants: 10
Organiser: Waag
Location: Amsterdam, The Netherlands

March

Open Day

9 March 2019
HACKademy Meet Up
Participants: 31
Organiser: Fablab Berlin (now Prototypes), be able e.V.
Location: Potsdam, Germany

Open Day

17 March 2019
HACKademy Meet Up
Participants: 70
Organiser: Fablab Berlin (now Prototypes), be able e.V.
Location: Potsdam, Germany

2019

February

3 February 2019
HACKademy Meet Up
Participants: 29
Organiser: Fablab Berlin (now Prototypes), be able e.V.
Location: Potsdam, Germany

16 March 2019
Made 4 You series (Open Call) 3.2
Participants: 24
Organiser: Waag
Location: Amsterdam, The Netherlands

Open Day

9 March 2019
Made 4 You series (Open Call) 3.1
Participants: 24
Organiser: Waag
Location: Amsterdam, The Netherlands

Open Day

Open Day

Activity Report

iv. Maker Gatherings

Activity Report v. Presentations

June

7 June 2019
Health&care Summer school - Open talk
 Participants: 30
 Organiser: Opendot
 Location: Milan, Italy
 M4Y Representation: Opendot

Presentation

25-27 June 2019
Wear It Innovation Summit
 Participants: 500
 Organiser: Wear it
 Location: Berlin, Germany
 M4Y Representation: ZSI

Presentation

July

4-6 July 2019
User centred design healthcare
 Participants: 45
 Organiser: dotdotdot
 Location: Amsterdam, Netherlands
 M4Y Representation: Opendot

Presentation

4-5 July 2019
User centred design (UXD) Healthcare Amsterdam
 Participants: 100
 Organiser: Waag
 Location: Amsterdam, Netherlands
 M4Y Representation: Opendot

Presentation

8-10 July 2019
Internet of Manufacturing
 Participants: 20
 Organiser: MakerNet Alliance
 Location: Warsaw, Poland
 M4Y Representation: ZSI

Presentation

8-11 July 2019
The 17th International Open and User Innovation Conference #OUI2019
 Participants: University of Utrecht
 Organiser: n.a.
 Location: Utrecht, Netherlands
 M4Y Representation: KUL

Presentation

Presentation

20 & 27 October 2019
Meeting with Odoardo Picciolini

Participants: 4
 Organiser: TOG
 Location: Milan, Italy
 M4Y Representation: TOG

Presentation

21-27 October 2019
Mozfest 2019

Participants: 300
 Organiser: Mozilla Foundation
 Location: London, United Kingdom
 M4Y Representation: ZSI

7-8 October 2019
**Open and User Innovation Conference -
 The 17th International Conference**

Participants: 1000
 Organiser: University Utrecht,
 Copernicus Institute and University
 Social Entrepreneurship Initiative
 Location: Utrecht, The Netherlands
 M4Y Representation: KUL

Presentation

28 October 2019
**Meeting with CNR LECCO /Simone
 Pittaccio**

Participants: 4
 Organiser: TOG
 Location: Milan, Italy
 M4Y Representation: TOG

Presentation

2020

30 January 2020
Feminity

Participants: 25
Organiser: Waag
Location: Amsterdam, Netherlands
M4Y Representation: Waag

Presentation

February

5 February 2020
Careables Olinda Opening Session

Participants: 40
Organiser: Casa Criatura
Location: Olinda, Brazil
M4Y Representation: GIG

Presentation

5 February 2020
Meeting with Odoardo Picciolini

Participants: 4
Organiser: TOG
Location: Milan, Italy
M4Y Representation: TOG

Presentation

March

8-11 March 2020
World Summit Award Vienna

Participants: 250
Organiser: WSA
Location: Vienna, Austria
M4Y Representation: ZSI

Presentation

April

16 April 2020
AI4EU Café fight against Corona virus

Participants: 50
Organiser: AI4EU project
Location: online (global)
M4Y Representation: ZSI

Presentation

17 April 2020
Design in times of ... corona

Participants: 816
Organiser: Pakhuis de Zwijger
Location: Amsterdam, Netherlands
M4Y Representation: Waag

Presentation

Presentation

7 May 2020
Re:publica 2020 TV edition

Participants: 16419
Organiser: republica GmbH
Location: online (global)
M4Y Representation: Waag

Presentation

21 May 2020
Viral Response Roundtable: Building open hardware communities in response to Covid-19

Participants: 40
Organiser: Wikifactory
Location: online (global)
M4Y Representation: ZSI

May

4-5 May 2020
Maker Faire Vienna

Participants: 100
Organiser: Innoc, Happylab, Maker Magazin
Location: Vienna, Austria
M4Y Representation: ZSI

Presentation

21 May 2020
A distributed answer to a global crisis: ideas, communities and rules

Participants: 603
Organiser: DDMP project together with Careables
Location: online (Italy)
M4Y Representation: Opendot & KUL

Presentation

29 May 2020
Saúde, Cuidado y tecnología: una relación atemporal

Participants: 278
Organiser: Procomu
Location: online (Brazil)
M4Y Representation: GIG

Presentation

Presentation

19 September 2020
Aziende e Makers – il contributo delle Aziende durante l'epidemia

Participants: Online
 Organiser: Maker faire Torino
 Location: Turin, Italy
 M4Y Representation: Opendot

Presentation

24 September 2020
DOIT Conference: Making Social Innovators

Participants: n.a
 Organiser: DOIT, Salzburg Research, St. Virgil Salzburg Hotel
 Location: online
 M4Y Representation: ZSI

Presentation

3 October 2020
Application of co-design method and the development of a toolkit to support the generation of innovative solution in healthcare

Participants: 100
 Organiser: Shaping for the future of pediatrics
 Location: Rome, Italy
 M4Y Representation: Opendot

October

20 September 2020
Festival delle abilità - Opendot e TOG, digital for social

Participants: 25
 Organiser: Festival delle Abilità
 Location: Milan, Italy
 M4Y Representation: Opendot & TOG

Presentation

29 September 2020
CheRRies project webinar series

Participants: 20
 Organiser: CHERRIES project
 Location: online (global)
 M4Y Representation: ZSI

Presentation

WEBINAR 2
"RRI PRACTICES IN HEALTHCARE"
 29 September 2020 | 12:30-13:30

SESSION SUMMARY
 Key questions leading the webinar:
 - How can RRI improve innovation practices in the healthcare sector?
 - Is the Responsible Research and Innovation framework developed enough to embrace such a complex ecosystem (the healthcare one)?
 - How can makers contribute to more accessible, collaborative and innovative healthcare solutions?
 - How responsible practices can contribute to the definition of impactful solutions to the healthcare challenges posed by COVID-19 pandemic?

REGISTRATION
 Go to webinar - Sign up here

SPEAKERS

Dr. Barbara Kiesiger
 Centre for Social Innovation

Rosha Melagrida
 VU University of Amsterdam

SPEAKER
 Dr. Barbara Kiesiger

SESSION DESCRIPTION

November

Presentation

17- 26 November 2020
Careables Maker Gathering Brazil

Participants: tbc
Organiser: Instituto ProComum
and Casa Criatura
Location: online (Brazil)
M4Y Representation: GIG

Presentation

29-30 November 2020
Manufacture 4.0 - exhibition
co-design method for health & care

Participants: 250
Organiser: Manifatture aperte
Location: Milan, Italy
M4Y Representation: Opendot

5 October 2020
TecnoTOG _ La tecnologia applicata alla
riabilitazione neurologica infantile

Participants: 135
Organiser: TOG
Location: Milan, Italy
M4Y Representation: Opendot & TOG

Presentation

14-15 October 2020
Knowledge for Change: A decade of
Citizen Science (2020-2030) in support of
the SDGs

Participants: n.a.
Organiser: CoAct, Museum Naturkunde Berlin,
ECSA, Germany's 2020 EU Council presidency
Location: Berlin, Germany
M4Y Representation: ZSI & Prototypes

Presentation

Activity Report

vi. Exhibitions

2018

July

Exhibition

5 July 2018
Made 4 You series (Open Call) 1.8
Participants:
Organiser: Waag
Location: Amsterdam, the Netherlands
M4Y Representation: Waag

October

Exhibition

16-17 October 2018
Grand Challenges Annual Meeting
Participants: 100
Organiser: Grand Challenges
Annual Meeting
Location: Berlin, Germany
M4Y Representation: Prototypes

November

Exhibition

5-25 November 2018
Reprocity Design.Liege
Participants: n.a.
Organiser: Province de Liege
Location: Various locations, Belgium
M4Y Representation: Open Dot

20-28 October 2018
MakeHealth expo @ Embassy of Health
Participants: 12000
Organiser: Dutch Design Week
Location: Eindhoven, the Netherlands
M4Y Representation: Waag

Exhibition

careables.org

Community map

For more up-to-date information, please visit [our website](#).

Europe

AUSTRIA

Centre for Social Innovation // Zentrum für Soziale Innovation
Linke Wienzeile 256, 1150 Vienna
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HappyLab
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https://happylab.at/de_vie/
Contact
Roland Stelzer
<https://www.fablabs.io/labs/happylab>

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www.law.kuleuven.be/citip/en

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Ilica 69, 10000, Zagreb
<https://www.fablab.hr/hr/osnovna/>

GERMANY

Agile Heap
Germany
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Erkelenzdam 59, 10961 Berlin
<https://prototypes.berlin/>

be able e.V.
Wilhelmine-Gemberg-Weg 12
10179 Berlin, Germany
<https://be-able.info/de/be-able/>

Beuth Hochschule Berlin, Labor für Fertigungsverfahren der Mechatronik
Luxemburger Straße 10 13353 Berlin, Germany
<https://labor.beuth-hochschule.de/fvm/>
Contact: Tasso Mulzer

Europe

GERMANY

Global Innovation Gathering e.V.
Wilhelmine-Gemberg-Weg 14
10179 Berlin, Germany
www.globalinnovationgathering.org/

Citylab Berlin
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Platz der Luftbrücke 4,
12101 Berlin, Germany
Contact: Sara Reichert

MachBar PotsdamfreiLand,
Friedrich-Engels-Strasse 22,
14473 Potsdam, Germany
<https://machbar-potsdam.de/>
Contact: Martin Koll

ITALY

Open Dot
Via Tertulliano 70 (entrance at n ° 68)
20137 Milano
www.opendotlab.it/

TogetherToGo Foundation
Italy
Milan
Viale Famagosta, 75
20142 Milan
<https://togethertogo.org/>

**Fondazione I.R.C.C.S.
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The Netherlands

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The Netherlands

Asia

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nepal.communitere.org

SINGAPORE

Engineering Good
201 Henderson Road,
#06-19 Apex@Henderson,
Singapore
<https://engineeringgood.org/>

Middle East

IRAQ

Science Camp
61001 Basra
<https://www.facebook.com/Iraqimakerspace>

Africa

GHANA

Kumasi Hive

Hse 49 – SE 29056 Drive, 2nd Turn
Behind Mizpah School
Kentinkrono –
Kumasi,
Ghana
<https://kumasihive.com/>

CAMEROON

MboaLab

31066, Yaoundé
<https://www.mboalab.africa/>

North & South America

THE UNITED STATES

e-Nable Global Community

21 Humboldt Street, Rochester New
York 14614, USA
<http://enablingthefuture.org>

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